

P: ISSN No. 2394-0344
E: ISSN No. 2455-0817

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

VOL.- X , ISSUE- II May - 2025
Remarking An Analisation

Exploring Ageism Through Lens of Intersectionality: A Take on Legal Right to Dignified Life for Geriatric Population in India

Paper Id : 20411 Submission Date : 2025-05-07 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-21 Publication Date : 2025-05-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16275418

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Abstract

Ageing is a universal and natural phenomenon, it doesn't possess with itself an age limit or a fixed definition because of involvement of biological, psychological and social factors being a part of it. Ageing is assumed to be that part of a human's life where the health and mind of people starts deteriorating in the terms of contribution to the society. This leads to the concept of Ageism, where the old people are discriminated because of their age and negative assumptions about them, to be specific about their contributory quotient in the society, both socially as well as economically. The aim of this research paper is to explore the right to equality and a dignified life and freedoms, which are the pillars of part 3 of the Indian Constitution, through the lens of Ageism and Intersectionality. The population growth of the older citizens in India has been high since the past few decades. The rapid industrialization and its impact on traditional family unions in the society, the bonding and affection amongst the family members have weakened making the lives of older citizens problematic due to being posed by economic, social and health security. Although the government has released a plethora of welfare schemes for the older citizens, they still remain as it is and nothing much is done in this era of globalisation to reduce the effects of ageism. There is a need for a stringent audit committee to look after the allocation and distribution of funds, so that these schemes remain corruption free. Another important findings of the study is to tackle the ageing issues families and children have to be more sensitive and their cognitive abilities must be recognised and utilized by the government and society.

Keywords Ageism, Intersectionality, Legal Right, Geriatric Population.

Introduction

Ageing being a natural phenomenon is bound to alter the proportion of a nation's population constituting the older generation which can or has at a certain point of time overpowered the proportion of the younger generations. The population growth of India is phenomenal, which can be observed from the fact that where it was projected to reach 1.38021 billion according to the 2021 census forecast, it now actually stands at 1.4 billion. However, the population of older people was projected aptly to be 143.25 million in 2021, with 470 million people of the nation. The rate of growth elderly population is much more positive as compared to the whole population of India. This simply means that the population of younger generation will be comparatively less or sometimes more than the geriatric aged ones. This depicts a sociological process which is expected to have its own share of social and cultural impacts on societal as well as state dimensions.

Though ageing is a universal and natural phenomenon, still it doesn't possess with itself an age limit or a fixed definition because of involvement of biological, psychological and social factors being a part of it. However, what is fixed or comes attached to or with ageing is vulnerability of old age people to be deprived of a dignified and healthy life. Ageing is assumed to be that part of a human's life where after the saturation of growth till mid-age (which is considered as a positive growth by the society), the health and mind of people starts deteriorating in the terms of contribution to the society. This leads to the concept of Ageism, where the old people are discriminated because of their age and negative

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assumptions about them, to be specific about their contributory quotient in the society, both socially as well as economically. This leads us to the intersectional factor of this research paper, which argues that the discrimination faced by a mid-age human in bound to be lesser as compared to a being of geriatric age, because of being vulnerable to diseases as well as ill social attitude. Also, since age being not an expressly excluded ground for discrimination under Article 15 of the Constitution of India, therefore, it is pertinent to explore the schemes brought in by states in order to eliminate this intersectionality which is leading to indirect discrimination.

Objective of study

The aim of this research paper is to explore the right to equality and a dignified life and freedoms, which are the pillars of part 3 of the Indian Constitution, through the lens of Ageism and Intersectionality so as to understand the unnoticed struggles of old age population of India due to highly prejudiced, biased, discriminatory behaviour of society and weak social welfare schemes on the part of the state to provide a sense of security. The paper will try to explore the prejudiced notions and assumptions about ageing and it's impact on the social and cultural lifestyle of the aged, middle age as well as young age people in the background of industrialization in the globalizing world where cultural exchange has supposedly impacted the Indian culture in realm of the western society.

Review of Literature

Sociology of ageing: A reader, Jaipur: Rawat Publications, 2009, ISBN 81-316-0190-0

This discourse sought to be set in flow by this edited publication aims to explore facets of older people in the social, economic and cultural arena. The themes that were sought to be insulated within this edition are firstly, ageing as a demographic, secondly, diversity amongst the aged population leading to heterogeneity in the discrimination faced by each of the diverse groups, and lastly the solution for the above two challenges in constructing sociology of ageing as a separate domain or discipline. The papers aim at exploring several theories of ageing for the purposes of supporting sociological researchers, and thereafter support its contents through empirical data. The papers have tried to resolve the debates on contemporary doubts related to ageing such as assumed lower health expectancy and deterioration through scientific lens and the concept of post-retirement life. Shifting from the concept and theories of ageing, the papers further dwell into the increasing impact of the ageing process on a nation's economy. It is pertinent to note that the edition has explicitly discussed the sufferings of aged people diagnosed with HIV/AIDS, firstly because of not being adequately attended and loose treatment and secondly, because of stigmas attached with the disease and old age. The edition also discusses the concept of active or positive ageing where ageing is used in a manner so as to utilise the experience of senior citizens in a way that is helpful for the industry as well as well-being of the aged. Shifting the discourse from economic to cultural aspects, the edition further lays its emphasis on marital status and societal engagements for the elderly ones. The papers further try to dwell deep and highlight the issues related to rural ageing through sub-disciplinary efforts by culling out and mapping the roots of the challenges. Although the book is a justified attempt to map the concept of ageing and ageism in an exhaustive manner, it somehow fails to incorporate the role of younger generations in the challenges faced by aged ones. It also fails to encapsulate the laws and policies to smoothen the phenomenon of ageing and its struggles, as law and society goes hand in hand, as their evolution depends on each other only, therefore it is pertinent to examine the impact of social stigmas and discrimination in the form of ageism on the society as a whole and how does policy makers have observed the issue in hand.

Amanalluha and Kumar Rajbeer, "The Legal Aspects of Rights of Senior Citizens and Their Maintenance in India" KRONIKA Journal (ISSN No. – 0023-4923) Volume 25 Issue 2 2025 "The rights and maintenance of senior citizens in India are protected under a comprehensive legal framework, with the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents under Senior Citizens Act, 2007, however the effective implementation of these laws remains a challenge due to lack of awareness, social stigma and inadequate infrastructure. By strengthening the legal and social support systems, raising awareness, and ensuring strict enforcement of maintenance orders, India can ensure that its senior citizens can live with dignity and security."

Main Text

Theoretical Framework:

Intersectionality:

Researchers have turned their attention to a growing range of social and cultural variables in the society like age, sex, gender, economic status, rural people, urban population, etc. making the fight for rights and equity different for each stratum of the

society. However, as per the theory of intersectionality, all the social groups are connected amongst themselves by some way or the other. It is this interdependency and interconnection which the theory of intersectionality aims to explore. And for the purposes of this paper, intersectionality simply represents the junction of two kinds of discrimination, or interaction between two forms of discrimination, and the study of that junction or what we may call double discrimination is the motto of intersectionality. Intersectionality tends to erase the boundaries drawn by essentialism which compartmentalises humans into one or the other social groups without considering the scenario of that person being a part of other groups as well. To understand this let us take an example, suppose a in America, homosexuals are a social group who are vulnerable to discrimination. Another marginalized group is that of blacks in the America who are prone to discrimination at various sectors of society. So, the concept of essentialism will make two separate groups, one for homosexuals and the other for blacks and will study about the discrimination of these two groups separately. However, practically there might be blacks who are homosexuals as well, so do they suffer double discrimination or not, is the approach which intersectional study will explore by erasing the boundaries of essentialism.

Social Identity Theory:

Now with the discourse on intersectionality, the researcher would move ahead with discrimination and ageism shedding light on theories and mechanisms that help social science researchers to unravel the causes, outcomes and to construct positive policies in order to intervene in the atrocious conditions of the elderly. Shifting our discourse to social identity theory, originated and developed by Tajfel and Turner (1979), the theory explores the facets and factors of the social groups which shapes the self-identity of its members. Interpreting Ageism through the lens of this theory suggests that negative stereotypes against the older individuals in the society to whom they belong, can inhibit the feeling of inferiority and weakness amongst the older individuals, for even those who are not so. This inhibition of inferiority can lead towards disturbed psychological and physiological well-being. This theory examines the impact of age-based biased attitude on the older population, which is discovered to be directly proportional to each other. Another theory that runs on the similar line is that of Stereotype embodiment theory, proposed by Levy (2009), which proposes that stereotypes against older population has a direct impact on physiological and cognitive abilities of them. Therefore, the increased struggles of the older population, if it is there in a state, is because of the negative and stereotyped notions running throughout the society which itself is the cause of deteriorated conditions of the elderly ones.

Stigma Theory:

Thereafter, it is pertinent to discuss the Stigma theory which drives the root cause for silent sufferings and isolations of the older population, hence making them vulnerable to indirect discrimination. This theory proposes that the people who deviate from the norms and set standards of behavioural patterns in the society are stigmatized and are bound to face negative attitude of the people around. And, from the fear of facing such an attitude the vulnerable people like older ones, decides to keep their sufferings to themselves and act to behave normal leading to silent suffering. Due to stigmatization, the older ones either have to suffer silently or who can't do so, either gets isolated by the society or themselves decides to be isolated in order to avoid the feeling of inferiority. The root cause behind such silent sufferings and ageism can be explored through Socioecological Model of theoretical frame which confers that the human behaviour is a result of interplay of specific facets like individualistic (representing intrapersonal features), interpersonal (interaction amongst peers and family members), organizational (generally related to workplace and official capacity), societal (state policies, rules and framework to support different sections of society according to their needs and requirements) and community (society as a whole with availability of resources to sustain peacefully) . Therefore, in order to understand the cause of ageism it is important to socioecological status of a state with respect to its older population.

Research Questions

Q1: How And When Does Fundamental Rights Fail To Empower The Aged Ones?

The term Justice which has been flamboyantly classified into Social, Economic and Political has been considered as the flagbearer of India's development. And to be specific, the term social justice represents a method or mechanism of removing differences in the needs of different section of society by harmonising the conflicting demands and establishing equality of status and living standards through equal opportunities and equitable access to resources for sustainable development of all. Although the term Justice is flexible and inclusive in nature, with the passage of almost a

quarter of 21st century, there have emergence of novel challenges which were not foreseen by the framers of Indian Constitution back then in 1940s.

One of such novel challenge is rights of elderly population of India, to be specific right to lead a dignified and healthy life with appropriate safety, security and dependence. To understand the legal scenario, assistance to the ones suffering from 'undeserved want' like the unemployed, sick and disabled or old aged persons. Before, moving ahead with the interpretation of this Article, the researcher would like to bring notice to the words used to stereotype old aged people with disabled ones and underserving bearers. This simply represents the notion of the constitution makers who considered old aged people similar to the ones who were disabled and are bound to be unemployed. This notion of the Constitution makers can be reaffirmed by the absence of old age people from the purview of Article 39 which assures right to equitable working conditions for men, women and children. Thereafter, moving towards the interpretation of the words 'Undeserving Want', the term sounds highly derogatory for the respective sections of the society discussed under Article 41. The term undeserving simply means non-meritorious or unjustified. However, providing aid to its citizens is the duty of a state, and duty to serve the unjust is what is implied from the wordings of Article 41.

Age is a natural process and at some point, of life or the other, human either adolescents or aged have to be dependent on other human beings. In order to enforce such dependence, the two judge bench of Supreme Court, has dealt with writ petition enforcing Article 21 of the Indian Constitution through issues related to pension funding, geriatric support, shelter aid, and enforcement of Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2008 (herein after referred to as 'the Act').¹ In order to support its argument regarding pension, the Petitioner vehemently established that which is possible only with the access to just amount of food, cloth and shelter which require adequate finances and therefore, the supreme court was requested to revise the then ongoing pension scheme² under which the beneficiaries used to get only Rs. 200/- per month for people between 60 to 79 and Rs. 500/- for 80 and above.

The contention was also raised against the meek enforcement of schemes for medical services and shelter homes for older people, however the defence taken by the government through solicitor general was regarding lack of finances. The important point to be noted through this judgement is that this Court has recognized all the rights related to old-age shelter homes, medical facilities in government hospitals and pension for the older population to be a part of right of dignified life being a facet of Article 21 of the Indian Constitution. Therefore, the court asserted theoretically that economic factors should step back when the issue pertains to enforcement of fundamental rights. However, taking a pragmatic view of the issue present before the division bench, economic factors do pay a role when it comes to establishing shelter homes for the aged ones, it is at this point where the court should restrain itself from involving in administrative features of the Constitution.

The Supreme Court has vehemently asserted that the situation in India is much more complicated which is a byproduct of industrialization and globalization leading to migration of family members leaving behind the older members in the rural areas.³ Although these older people are not destitute or to simply put, not in need of shelter homes, but they still need assistance to maintain the shelter and they do depend on someone for that. These people are ready to pay for the assistance and in these scenarios, they become vulnerable to falling for gimmicks and undue influence by the other members of the society. This is how ageism leads to vulnerability of being deprived of their fundamental right for the older people to lead a safe, secure and healthy life. Therefore, pertaining to this issue, the court took a strong stand in favour of the petitioners and conferred that it has been more than half a decade for the government failing to enforce the policies and the Act, and if further delay is done, then the purpose of these policies would fall against the nation state. Therefore, this court decided to Indira Gandhi National Old-age Pension Scheme, 1955 ³ Supra, footbote 1, Para. 27 issue a continuous mandamus against the Government of India, and suggested the states and union to work conjunctively in order to achieve the goals of the Act and geriatric policies.

The Sociology of Family Amid Industrialization

The researcher through this paper aims to present several causes of vulnerability starting from basic unit of society i.e., family to discrimination at workplace. Since, family is the building block of a society, it is pertinent to examine the changing features of this unit in order to cull out the root cause of ageism. Traditionally, the Indian society was embedded with joint family units which followed the ideology of Mutual or Common responsibility for all its members. The breadwinner used to pool in the earnings for the well-being of every member and every member was responsible to take care of each other. Each and every family member had defined responsibility with the older ones in the decision making and

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guidance authority primarily to preserve the culture and heritage of the family. However, with the urbanization and industrialization these clearly demarcated roles have blurred. It has been observed that nuclear families are more appealing and flexible when it comes to maintain the work-life balance for the current generation. With the growth in urbanization, education and job opportunities for all and specially for women has made themselves evolve from the traditional roles essayed in their joint families, making a shift towards growth and independence.⁴ The important point to be noted here is that, although men and women of joint families have evolved from their stereotyped roles, the elderly ones couldn't. This is another point of psychological and thematic research, in order to examine, whether ageing reduces the capacity or ability of a being to evolve and adapt to modern lifestyle? It is probably the conflict between the conservative role which on aged family member stands by and the evolved and modern roles assumed by the younger generation, which is the root cause of ageism through abandonment of senior citizens by their younger generation family members.⁵ The persisting issue that comes before the society is whether education and urbanization which has become a source of independence and empowerment of many humans and specially women in the contemporary times, acts as a latent cause of vulnerability of the elders.

And, the fact that should be examined or explored is that, whether the polices are made in a manner to resolve this latency, either by empowering.

Feminist Neglect of Ageism:

As per the observations of Calasanti, 2006⁶ the feminist scholars since ages have neglected to consider and study the struggles of old people and have restricted themselves to young age to middle age women. It seemed like the stigma theory attached to ageism has traversed through the minds of feminist jurists and they consider studying themselves as old in the form of a negative contention. As per Marshall, 2006⁷ the feminists keep beating around the bush without looking into the actual constraints or limitations of ageing. Although feminist scholars do try to challenge the stereotypes against ageism, but they somehow end up creating an additional struggle for the old people in order to remove the stigma. Suppose, feminists promote the notion that even in old age, a person can be active and do stressful jobs in order to kill the notions of ageism, then those who are actually unable to remain active due to ageing will definitely feel excluded or isolated from the society, which would be nothing but aggravating the situation. This is so because, the feminist scholars have a limited scope of vision pertaining to ageing.

Q2: How Is The Legal Recourse Available To Abandoned And Neglected Senior Citizens In India Paves The Way For Revival Of Their Dignified Life?

The major source of protection that could be availed by senior citizens is the central legislation i.e., MWPC Act of 2007 which tends to regulate the rights of senior citizens and make justice accessible to them in the scenarios like neglect, destitution or abandonment. To cut through the whole legislation the researcher will specifically focus on the provisions remodifying the challenges of neglect and abandonment by the family members. The Act, specifically mentions of neglect in a very limited prospect of economic dependence. Section 9 of the Act specifically allows a senior citizen to approach the maintenance tribunal established under section 7 of the Act. This maintenance tribunal is supposed to pass order for maintenance in capacity court under the Code of Civil Procedure 1908, and once the order is finalized, it is considered as an order under the Code of Criminal Procedure 1973, for the purposes of its execution transforming the tribunal's character from civil to that of a criminal court. The ambit of neglect is way too restricted, for the purposes of which the judicial tribunal has been vested with the jurisdiction under section 5. The term Neglect under the Act has been specifically used to describe as economic neglect. When a person gets old, what he/she needs is something definitely not money but health and emotional maintenance. The socio and cultural dimension of ageism has been absurdly left out by policy makers in the Act. For senior citizens who do receive pensions, don't need economic support because the pension is supposed to be usually more than what could be allotted through the Act i.e., a mere amount of Rs. 10,000/- only. The duty to provide medical facilities have been completely levied on the respective state government that too through overburdened government hospitals under section 20. The word 'WELFARE' in the title of the Act, is completely unjustified by the provisions which only serves to the economic dimensions of Ageism. For a senior citizen receiving adequate maintenance, but incapacitated to use it diligently for impairment because of age or, in case suffering abuse, either direct or indirect within the four walls of the domestic premises by his/her family members there is not statutory recourse available to the aged victims.

Thereafter, for the purposes of Abandonment, it has been enshrined as a Criminal offence by the Act under section 24 and section 23 reflects the duties to protect and safeguard

the welfare of aged citizens by the beneficiaries to who they transferred some property. Well eventually the issues pertaining to neglect and abuse discussed hereinabove, of the aged family members have been catered to by the Chhattisgarh High Court where issue had a major chunk of portion in protection against exposure to torture and abandonment.⁸ In the case of being discussed at hand, the Petitioner husband and wife, being of the aged 89 and 77 years respectively, were not only cornered, captivated, neglected in their home owned by the husband, but also faced exposure to physical as well as mental and emotional abuse by their son and daughter-in-law. Fed up by the crude treatment in their own home and apprehension of danger to their lives and dignity, they approached the police to file a report. However, the police were unable to find a provision in the Act to accommodate the offence, and eventually registered the report against section 24 of the Act. While the petition was pending before Judicial magistrate first class as the court of first instance, the petitioners approached the magistrate with an interim application for ejection of their son and daughter-in-law, because of apprehension of threat to their life and dignity. Because of the absence of any provision for the same in the Act, the application was dismissed. Thereafter, a revision application was made against the order of Judicial magistrate first class, which was also dismissed. Therefore, the petitioners took the recourse of section 482 under CRPC and approached Chhattisgarh High court. The Chhattisgarh high court approved the application for interim ejection of the son and daughter-in-law in order to achieve the goals of the Act, and ultimately safeguarding the interests of the petitioners who were in need of 'protection', giving the term a wider meaning extending the ambit of section 23 to section 25 and generating protection of elderly one as the ultimate purpose of both the sections of the Act. An important point to be noted here is that, the court overstepped its role of limiting itself under the principle of judicial restraint, which simply means to abide by what law says and not to make the laws. This was done under the garb of reading down the act so as to determine its intended purpose. However, the struggle with the Act is still there as well noticed in this case itself, where the orders of lower courts were not able to see through the wordings of the Act, as every aged person won't be able to come so far down the legal journey to secure the ends of justice through the apex and high courts. This simply means, the courts will lower courts and won't act erroneously in rejecting the petitioners' complaint as their report doesn't fall within any offence of the specific law prescribed for the older ones. Therefore, it is inevitable to secure socio-economic and basic by expanding the ambit of the Act from simply being economic in nature to focusing on regulating the social and human rights violation starting from the basic unit of a society i.e., family.

Domestic Abuse As A Facet Of Ageism

Moving further with the discourse on elderly abuse, the domestic violence suffered by older citizen are multifaceted.⁹ Physical abuse might involve inflicting pain, harm, injury. It should also include within its ambit the act of or omission to take care of the medicinal, physiological or biological needs of the older people in order for intended deterioration of their health without an overt act of harm or injury. When it comes to psychological or emotional abuse, the domestic violence harms their mental capability to process things normally due to trauma or distress about abuse by rude and uncooperative family members. Emotional health is a factor which accelerate the ageing process by firstly diminishing the self-esteem and thereafter impacting the cognitive abilities of an elder citizen. Another and a kind of its own abuse which is most prevalent in the Indian society is the financial abuse, where an undue advantage of impairment and illness of the elderly are taken by their family members. In the Letters Patent Appeal in the case before Chandigarh High Court^[10], it was conferred that as per section 23, its s a mandate for the family members of an older citizen to take care of him/her, and the moral obligations laid down by the Act on its intended subjects are not to be restricted in case of restricted and grammatical interpretation of the letter of law. As per the Indian legal framework is considered, the only statute available against domestic abuse against older citizens is that of MWPC Act of 2007, and we have already discussed the limited ambit of the Act in favour of economic or maintenance support rather than protection against violence. The issue of timely enforcement is still subsistent, when can pose serious issues to the safety and well being of the elders through abuse by their family members of the buffer time available till orders are enforced.

Silence on the part of older ones to report the abuse happening or happened to them is another issue which should be catered to by the policy makers. The seasoned argument for such a reluctance is ignorance of law. The older citizens are not aware of the summary proceedings or laws made in their favour. Another reason that must be catered to is that there is no immediate relief available to the older citizen and he/she is supposed to fight the legal battle along with the apprehension of retaliation by family members and the society. In order to avoid such instances, it is important for the legal policies to introduce ideas like that of a living will, where the older citizen can plan for his last stages of life to pre-plan and maintain the development cycle for them as well. ^[11]

Measuring The Success of Policies And Schemes

As far as policies are concerned, the Indian government has framed several plans in favour of older citizens and to make their struggles lesser to deactivate the indirect discrimination going against them.¹² Some of these policies turned into welfare programmes are as follows: 1992 Integrated Programmes for Older Persons (IPOP). The welfare scheme although aimed at providing economic, healthcare, legal, recreational facilities somehow failed due uneven application across different states, and with a distinct attitude in urban and rural areas. Like the places where local self-government was strong like in Delhi, the awareness was also proportional amongst the older citizens as compared to weak governance in states like Jharkhand, which ultimately reflected on the living standards of the older citizens there. Another scheme that deserves the attention is the National old age pension scheme (NOAPS), 1995 which aimed at providing some sort of economic support to the people above 65 years of age and who are below the poverty line. Now the major challenge faced by this scheme implementation was the identification of eligible and intended beneficiaries, which somehow became more troublesome in rural areas due to the village population being unaware and due to absence of proper documentation for the enrolment scheme. Thereafter, the National policy for Senior Citizens, 2011 started making waves due to its agenda based on a sociological approach to build the gap of affection between generations so as to incorporate the values of integration in the society. The policy failed miserably because of deviating from its agenda i.e., social inclusion of older citizens to just securing economic benefits to the Older. Due to lack of sufficient funds and absence of proper auditing mechanism, the policy couldn't be implemented. Discussing the pension schemes like Direct Benefits Transfer plan, 2013 and Atal Pension Scheme of 2015 which aimed at providing financial support form of pension to employees above 60 in unorganised employment sector in India, has been struggling on its path due to corruption allocation and distribution of funds both by the central as well as the state government.

Conclusion The population growth of the older citizens in India has been high since the past few decades. And with the rapid industrialization and its impact on traditional family unions in the society, the bonding and affection amongst the family members have weakened making the lives of older citizens problematic due to being posed by economic, social and health security. Although the government has released a plethora of welfare schemes for the older citizens, they still remain as it is and nothing much is done in this era of globalisation to reduce the effects of ageism. There is a need for a stringent audit committee to look after the allocation and distribution of funds, so that these schemes remain corruption free. Another important observation to be noted is that, even if supposedly the welfare schemes are implemented successfully, still the government can only make the older citizens available in the infrastructural and external support, but families and children need to be more sensitive and attentive to the needs of elderly. We need to rebound the family ties in order to promote family care through reinforcement of traditional values in school and college curriculums. Also when it comes to schemes and laws for reducing ageism, it is important for the policy makers to look beyond financial security and make the older capable of exercising their cognitive abilities by making them feel integrated into the society rather than just providing them with some money and making them sit with the four walls of institutional welfare.

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